

Understanding [3+2] cycloaddition reactions from the molecular electron density perspective: A new theoretical outlook on organic reactions

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Cycloaddition reactions share the top shelf priority in the toolbox of organic chemists owing to their diverse pharmaceutical and industrial applications. The frontier molecular orbital (FMO) theory has been used to study the reactivity of cycloaddition reactions since nearly the last five decades, though there have been criticisms, and even instances of failures. In 2016, an appealing alternative has been proposed by Domingo, namely the molecular electron density theory (MEDT), to underline the decisive role of changes in electron density in the observed molecular reactivity of chemical reactions. MEDT uses a set of advanced quantum chemical tools and has been extensively applied to analyze organic reactions, particularly focussed on cycloadditions in more than 250 studies since last six years to cover varied aspects such as reactivity, substituent effects, catalysis, solvent effects, strain promotion, regio-, stereo- and chemoselectivity. This article is intended to present a brief overview of MEDT for analysis of [3+2] cycloaddition reactions by experimentalists and theoretical chemists.

Keywords: MEDT, ELF, [3+2] cycloaddition reactions.

1. Introduction

Organic Compounds were historically characterized by the concept of “*vitalism*”, which has eventually been discredited with gradual advances in science and technology. Nevertheless, organic chemistry still continues to serve as the inevitable synthetic backbone of medicinal and applied sciences, the selectivity, reactivity and mechanistic aspects of organic reactions dictate the uniqueness of this branch of chemistry. Interpreting organic reactions are quite challenging owing to the structural diversity and varied reactivity of these compounds. The transition state theory¹ (TST) formulated the first bridging gap between experimental and theoretical sciences for analysis of chemical reactions. Energy transformations occurring in a chemical reaction can be well understood by studying the electronic structure and the changes in the bonding framework, which characterize the location of reactants, products, intermediates and transition states (TSS) along a reaction path as the molecular modelling studies approximate the Schrödinger’s equation². The concepts of hybridization, inductive effect and resonance are within the valence bond theory³⁻⁵ (VBT), while the molecular orbital theory⁶ (MOT) applies the Born Oppenheimer’s approximation⁷, to propose that electrons are not localized on one nucleus, while the potential field of all the nuclei influence the movement of the electron. In 1952, Fukui *et al.*⁸ proposed the frontier molecular orbital (FMO) theory, considering the Hückel’s molecular orbital theory⁹⁻¹¹ in which the chemical reactivity is interpreted in terms of the MOs generated from the valence AOs (atomic orbitals). Cycloaddition reactions were analyzed using the FMO concept in several studies of 1960-70s by Woodward and Hoffman¹², Pearson¹³ and Houk¹⁴. The FMO theory has also witnessed failures¹⁵ and serious critiques by Dewar¹⁶ from the late 1980s. However, the continuing popularity since the last four-five decades of FMO theory in analysing cycloaddition reactions is due to its simplicity.

The evolution of molecular modelling since the last two decades has allowed successful correlation of the experimental

findings and the theoretical concepts, after the proposal of Density Functional theory¹⁷ (DFT) based on the Hohenberg and Kohn theorem¹⁸ using Kohn-Sham equations¹⁹. A diverse range of quantum chemical tools were applied by Domingo on several organic reactions, particularly focussed on cycloaddition reactions to propose the molecular electron density theory²⁰⁻²² (MEDT) in 2016 which states that changes in electron density are responsible for molecular reactivity. As an appealing alternative to the FMO concept, more than 250 publications on MEDT applications to organic reactions have been published since last 6 years in reputed high impact international journals. In 2018, the Diels Alder (DA) reaction²³ of 1,3-butadiene and ethylene was studied by Domingo from the MEDT perspective. The reaction was characterized as the non-polar one with the high activation enthalpy of 23.2 kcal mol⁻¹ and the sequence of bonding changes along the reaction path could be analyzed using the quantum chemical tools. The competitiveness of Lewis acid catalysed polar DA reaction and polar Alder-ene reaction has also been analyzed from the MEDT perspective²⁴. Several interesting aspects of [3+2] cycloaddition (32CA) reactions such as strain promotion²⁵⁻²⁷, catalysis^{28,29}, substituent effects^{30,31}, regio-³²⁻³⁴, stereo-³²⁻³⁴ and chemo-selectivity^{35,36} have been successfully analyzed using the MEDT concept. Herein, we present a brief overview of MEDT, the methodology and its applications to analyze the reactivity, selectivity and mechanistic aspects of [3+2] cycloaddition (32CA) reactions.

2. Correlating electronic structure and molecular reactivity by ELF study

Within the MEDT framework, the so-called terminology “1,3-dipole” is replaced by “three atom components or TACs”²⁰, since the electronic distribution determining the bonding pattern of these reagents participating in 32CA reactions result from the varied nature and relative positions of the reacting nuclei, which doesn't consider charges but the whole molecular electron density. The electron localization function (ELF) proposed by Becke and Edgecombe³⁷, allows a

mathematical representation of the electronic structure; this was further extended by Silvi and Savin³⁸ to identify electronic regions in a chemical system, namely the bonding, non-bonding and the core attractors. The bonding attractors are located between the two nuclei, the non-bonding attractors on the single nuclei associated with the non-bonding electron density or *pseudoradical* center, while the core attractors are located at the nuclei positions. Basin of an attractor is characterized as monosynaptic, disynaptic, polysynaptic on the basis of one, two or more number of associated nuclei. The ELF localization domains of ethylene, styrene, methyl acrylate and nitroethylene are shown in Fig. 1. Note that the green domains indicate the basins corresponding to the bonding attractors located in between two nuclei, while the red ones are located over oxygen in methyl acrylate and nitroethylene indicating the non bonding electron density.

Fig. 1. ELF localization domains [Isovalue: 0.79] of ethylene, styrene, methyl acrylate and nitroethylene. Protonated basins are shown in light green, disynaptic basins are shown in deep green, monosynaptic basins are shown in red and core basins are shown in black colours.

The ELF valence basin population can be computed by integrating the basins, which allow defining *pseudoradical* and carbenoid center within MEDT. A monosynaptic basin integrating 1 e is classified as a *pseudoradical* center, while that inte-

grating c.a. 2 e is a carbenoid center. Depending on the electronic structure, TACs can be classified into four types, namely the *pseudodiradical*, *pseudo(mono)radical*, carbenoid and zwitter-ionic ones. The *pseudodiradical* TACs consist of two *pseudoradical* centers, while the, *pseudo(mono)radical* TACs are associated with one *pseudoradical* center. Presence of a carbenoid center classifies a carbenoid TAC, while the absence of both *pseudoradical* and carbenoid centers characterize a zwitter-ionic TAC. The reactivity of TACs in 32CA reactions follows the order³⁴

pseudodiradical > *pseudo(mono)radical* ≈ carbenoid > zwitter-ionic

The electronic structures of the TACs are represented in Fig. 2. Azomethine ylides³⁹ are generally classified as *pseudodiradical* TACs, and are associated with unappreciable energy barrier and highest reactivity along the series, consistent with the experimental studies. The reactivity of, *pseudo(mono)radical* and carbenoid TACs are comparable and relatively lower than that of the *pseudodiradical* ones. Azomethine imines⁴⁰ and nitrile imines⁴¹/ylides represent the *pseudo(mono)radical* and carbenoid type of TACs respectively. The lowest reactivity is shown by the zwitter-ionic TACs with high energy barrier. Nitrones³⁴ represent one of the examples of the zwitter-ionic TACs.

Fig. 2. Electronic structure of the four types of TACs participating in 32CA reactions.

3. Analysis of the reactivity indices defined within the conceptual density functional theory (CDFT)

The conceptual density functional theory⁴² (CDFT) indices have been applied in numerous cycloaddition reactions⁴³ to pre-

dict the electrophilic or nucleophilic behaviour of the reagents and hence to predict the polar character of the reaction, while the local indices characterize the most electrophilic and nucleophilic sites for prediction of the regioselectivity. The commonly used global and local CDFT indices for cycloaddition reactions are as follows:

a. *Electronic Chemical Potential*⁴⁴ (μ) denotes the tendency of a molecule to exchange electron density and can be calculated from the HOMO and LUMO energies:

$$\mu \approx \frac{(E_{\text{HOMO}} + E_{\text{LUMO}})}{2}$$

b. *Chemical Hardness*⁴⁵ (η) is the measure of the resistance to share electron density with the environment, while *Chemical Softness* (S) is the inverse of chemical hardness. η can be expressed mathematically in terms of the ionization potential I and electron affinity A as follows:

$$\eta \approx \frac{I - A}{2}$$

This expression can be approximated in terms of the HOMO (E_{HOMO}) and LUMO (E_{LUMO}) energies by using Koopman's Theorem⁴⁶.

$$\eta \approx \frac{(E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}})}{2}$$

The factor $\frac{1}{2}$ in the above expression is generally neglected and accordingly, η is given by⁴³

$$\eta \approx E_{\text{LUMO}} - E_{\text{HOMO}}$$

c. *Electrophilicity Index*^{47,48} (ω) classifies the molecule as a strong, moderate or marginal electrophile and is given by:

$$\omega = \frac{\mu^2}{2\eta}$$

Electrophilicity index above 1.50 eV calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory classifies the molecule as a strong electrophile, while those below 0.80 eV are the marginal electrophiles within the standard electrophilicity scale⁴⁸. Molecules with the electrophilicity index between 0.80 eV and 1.50 eV are classified as the moderate electrophiles.

d. *Nucleophilicity index*,⁴⁹ (N) classifies the molecule as a strong, moderate or marginal nucleophile and is given as the difference in HOMO energy of the molecule from that of tetracyanoethylene (TCE).

$$N = E_{\text{HOMO(Nucleophile)}} - E_{\text{HOMO(TCE)}}$$

Nucleophilicity index above 3.00 eV calculated at B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory classifies the molecule as a strong nucleophile, while those below 2.00 eV are the marginal electrophiles within the standard nucleophilicity scale⁴⁹. Molecules with the nucleophilicity index between 2.00 eV and 3.00 eV are classified as the moderate nucleophiles.

e. *Fukui Functions*: These functions represent the local CDFT indices proposed by Yang and Mortier⁵⁰ to characterize the electrophilic and nucleophilic centers in a molecule and consequently predict the regioselectivity of the reaction. The Fukui function for nucleophilic attack is given as the difference between the atomic charge of the species at the site r containing $(N+1)$ and (N) number of electrons, while that for electrophilic attack is given as the difference between the atomic charge of the species at the site r containing (N) and $(N-1)$ number of electrons

$$f^+(r) \approx \rho_{N+1}(r) - \rho_{N_0}(r) \text{ (For nucleophilic attack)}$$

$$f^-(r) \approx \rho_{N_0}(r) - \rho_{N-1}(r) \text{ (For electrophilic attack)}$$

The local electrophilicity⁵¹ ω_k index at site k is expressed as the multiplication of the global electrophilicity ω index with the Fukui function for nucleophilic attack

$$\omega_k = \omega f_k^+$$

The local nucleophilicity⁵² N_k index at site k is expressed as the multiplication of the global nucleophilicity N index with the

Fukui function for electrophilic attack

$$N_k = Nf_k^-$$

f. Parr Functions: These local CDFT indices represent higher precision relative to the Fukui functions and were proposed by Domingo in 2013^{53,54}. The atomic spin densities (ASDs) ρ_s^{rc} (r) and ρ_s^{ra} (r) at the reacting sites of the radical cation and radical anion are employed instead of charges for calculation of the Parr functions, which are given by:

$$P^+ (r) = \rho_s^{ra} (r) \text{ (for nucleophilic attack)}$$

$$P^- (r) = \rho_s^{rc} (r) \text{ (for electrophilic attack)}$$

Accordingly, the local electrophilicity and local nucleophilicity indices are calculated from the Parr functions at the reacting sites.

4. Energy profile study by exploring the potential energy surfaces

Computational chemistry studies involve modelling the nuclear configurations along the reaction path through which the reactants are transformed into the products. In 2006, Sutcliffe⁵⁵ proposed the concept of potential energy surface (PES), stating that the molecular geometries along the reaction paths are each associated with a potential energy. Analysis of the stationary points along the PES allows location and characterization of the reactants, intermediates, transition states (TSs) and products. The selectivity and reactivity of 32CA reactions can be predicted theoretically by studying the energy profile of the stationary states. For example, in a recent MEDT study²⁸ for the 32CA reaction of 1-pyrroline-1-oxide (PNO) and 2,3-dihydrofuran (DHF) (Fig. 3), the generation of *ortho/exo* isomer (**CA-ox**) was predicted as the most feasible adduct with the lowered free energy of activation relative to that of the *ortho/endo* isomer (**CA-on**), *meta/exo* isomer (**CA-mx**) and *meta/endo* isomer (**CA-mn**), in complete agreement with the experiments, while the BF_3 catalyzed version of the 32CA reaction shows sharp decrease in activation free energy, consistent with the experimentally observed faster Lewis acid catalyzed reaction. The polar character of a chemical reaction

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Fig. 3. Free energy of activation (calculated at ω B97XD/6-311G(d,p) level of theory in dichloromethane at 25°C) for the studied reaction paths associated with the uncatalyzed and BF_3 catalyzed 32CA reactions of 1-pyrroline-1-oxide PNO 1 and 2,3-dihydrofuran DHF 2.

can be determined by the calculation of global electron density transfer⁵⁶ (GEDT) at the TSs, given by the sum of natural charges q at each reacting counterpart and is given as,

$$\text{GEDT}(f) = \sum_{q \in f} q$$

Reactions with GEDT values above 0.2 e are classified as the polar processes. Thus, a fruitful interplay of the theory and experiment can be established for the 32CA reaction by following the PES and determination of the polar character. In 2017, Domingo⁵⁷ established that in polar Diels Alder (DA) reactions, the C-C double bond experiences depopulation due to the bonding changes in the two reacting moieties caused by the high GEDT. Consequently, polar reactions show decrease in the activation energy and take place easily relative to the non-polar ones. In 2019, Domingo *et al.*⁵⁸ reported the influence of GEDT on the nature of organic electron density transfer complexes.

5. Revealing the plausible mechanism through bonding evolution theory (BET)

In 1997, Krokidis⁵⁹ proposed the conjunction of the electron localization function^{37,38} (ELF) and Thom's catastrophe theory⁶⁰, to structure the plausible mechanism of chemical reactions, namely the bonding evolution theory (BET). Herein, the intrinsic reaction coordinate⁶¹ (IRC) along the reaction path is followed and the ELF is calculated at each point to identify the *phases*, which allows dividing the reaction path into different ELF topological phases. The BET concept has been employed in several studies⁶²⁻⁶⁴ to structure the plausible molecular mechanism of chemical reactions. Recently, we have analyzed the intramolecular 32CA (IM32CA) reactions of *C,N*-disubstituted nitrones from the MEDT perspective⁶⁵. Fig. 4 shows the simplified representation of the proposed mechanism arising from the topological analysis of the ELF. This 32CA reaction involves nine ELF phases and the IRC points S_0 -I to S_8 -I denote the starting point of each phase along the reaction pathway. The most significant ELF valence basin population at these IRC points are represented in Fig. 4. Minimal GEDT at

the TS characterizes this 32CA reaction as the non-polar one consistent with high activation energy barrier. The ELF of the first phase starting at S_0 -I is similar to that of the reactants, while the second phase starting at S_1 -I is characterized by the formation of non-bonding electron density at N2 integrating 0.85 e. The third phase shows rupture of the olefinic double bond, while the formation of *pseudoradical* center at the C3 carbon takes place in *phase IV*, starting at S_3 -I and that at C4 carbon takes place in *phase V*, starting at S_4 -I. The transition state is found in *phase IV*, suggesting that the activation energy is associated with the formation of non-bonding electron density at N2, rupture of the C4-C5 bond and formation of *pseudoradical* center at C3. The formation of C3-C4 single bond takes place by coupling of the *pseudoradical* centers at C3 and C4 carbon in *phase VI*, starting at S_5 -I, while the *pseudoradical* center at C5 is created in *phase VII* starting at S_6 -I. Finally, the non-bonding electron density at O1 is created in *phase VIII* starting at S_7 -I which couples with the *pseudoradical* center at C5 to form the O1-C5 single bond in *phase IX* starting at S_8 -I and the molecular geometry is relaxed in the cycloadduct.

6. Characterization of the interactions from AIM and NCI studies

The analysis of QTAIM (Quantum theory of atoms in molecules) parameters proposed by Bader and coworkers^{66,67} allow characterizing the type of interactions at the TSs. The QTAIM parameters namely the total electron density $\rho(r_c)$ and Laplacian of electron density $\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$ are calculated at the bond critical points (BCPs). Accumulation of the total electron density below 0.1 e and positive value of the Laplacian $\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$ is indicative of the non-covalent interactions, while the negative Laplacian and the total electron density above 0.1 e at the BCPs imply the covalent interactions. The non-covalent interactions (NCIs) can be characterized as the strongly repulsive, strongly attractive or weak interactions using the independent gradient model⁶⁸ (IGM) analysis. Fig. 5 shows the IGM isosurface of the TSs associated with 32CA reactions of trimethylsilyldiazo-alkanes with diethyl fumarate proposed in a

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recent MEDT study⁶⁹. Note that the so called “steric interactions” due to the presence of trimethylsilyl group is also observed as the green coloured isosurface.

Fig. 5. IGM analysis for visualisation of non-covalent interactions in the TSs associated with 32CA reactions of trimethylsilyldiazoalkanes with diethyl fumarate.

7. Conclusion

Owing to the evolution of advanced software applications, computational chemistry has witnessed significant development since the last decade. The molecular electron density theory (MEDT) underlines the decisive role of changes in electron density along the reaction path for interpretation of organic reactivity by using diverse quantum chemical tools. Within the MEDT perspective, the ELF study at the ground state (GS) of the reagents is performed initially to correlate the electronic

structure and the molecular reactivity. The CDFT indices at the GS of the reagents are calculated to initially comprehend the polar character. The reactivity and selectivity are predicted by location of the stationary points along the potential energy surface and the plausible mechanism is structured from the bonding evolution theory analysis. Finally, the topological analysis of the ELF and the AIM at the TSs allow characterizing the interactions. As the concluding remark, MEDT has emerged as a reliable alternative for the analysis of organic reactions.

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UNESCO-UNDP Fellow USA (1982) at Pennsylvania State University and other Universities. He has extensively visited several countries, and delivered invited lectures at a number of Universities and International Conferences. After his retirement from University of Calcutta he was attached as Sir Asutosh Mookerjee Fellow (ISCA-DST) with the Central Ayurveda Research Institute of Drug Development, CCRAS, Kolkata (2016-2021). He was General Secretary, *Indian Science Congress Association* in 2006-2009, having previously served as Treasurer (2004-2006), and Sectional President in Chemistry (1996-1997). He has had a long association with the *Indian Chemical Society*, serving as Council member, Treasurer, Honorary Secretary (1990-1993) and Vice-President (1996-1997, 2000-2001). He represented the ICS in the *Federation of Asian Chemical Societies*, and was founder-member of the Board of *Asian Network on Research in Anti-Diabetic Plants (ANRAP)*. He has received a number of academic awards including the prestigious R. C. Mehrotra Memorial Lifetime Achievement Award {101st Session of ISCA, 2014}; 15th Mukarram Khundker Memorial Lecture (1998 - *Dhaka University*); *Indian Chemical Society* - Basudev Banerjee Award (1991), P. K. Bose Memorial Award (1993). He was nominated Fellow, West Bengal Academy of Science and Technology (from 1990), and Fellow of the Indian Science Congress Association (2019). He has been engaged in research involving diverse area of Organic Chemistry since 1967: Study of Natural Products on all aspects; [3+2] cycloadditions; Heterocyclic Chemistry; Computational Chemistry; NMR studies; Single Electron Transfer Reactions. He has published more than 170 papers, and has over 190 Abstracts in Proceedings of International and National Conferences/Symposia including several invited and plenary lectures. He has supervised 25 research scholars for Ph.D. degree.

Dr. Nivedita Acharjee

Dr. Nivedita Acharjee is currently working as Assistant Professor in Department of Chemistry, Durgapur Government College. After completing her B.Sc. (Honours) in Chemistry in 2003 from Lady Brabourne College, Kolkata, she completed M.Sc. in Chemistry from University of Calcutta in 2005. She completed her Ph.D. studies focussed on experimental studies of cycloaddition reactions under the guidance of Professor Avijit Banerji, University of Calcutta, in September 2011. She started working on the theoretical aspects of [3+2] cycloaddition reactions since 2010. She has research collaborations with Professor Luis R Domingo, University of Valencia, Spain, and also collaborates with several theoretical chemists of India and throughout the world. She has published more than 60 quality research papers, book chapters and articles in edited volumes. Her current research interest is focused on the analysis of organic reactions using the molecular electron density theory study (MEDT). She is a life member of Indian Science Congress Association.